

**Protein-Protein Network and Pathway Analysis of Differentially Expressed
Genes in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Therapy**

Divya Jhinharia, Samvedna Singh, Shakti Sahi

School of Biotechnology, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, India

Email: divyajhinharia69@gmail.com

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is caused by genetic, environmental, behavioral and other risk factors and characterized by hyperglycemia, insulin resistance (IR), and relative insulin deficiency. Herein, we aim to report the hub genes involved in type 2 diabetes mellitus by carrying differential gene expression analysis followed by their enrichment studies and pathways involved. Present study gives an account on the up-regulated and down-regulated genes which showed significant expression. Hub genes were selected to construct protein-protein networks. Among the differentially expressed genes, top five genes involved in type 2 diabetes mellitus therapy are taken into consideration for further enrichment analysis. Besides the evident genes like , insulin-like growth factor-binding protein (IBP1), insulin isoform 2 (INSR2) and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF1), other genes out of top five includes- glucokinase regulator(GCKR), free fatty acid receptor 3 (FFAR3), adenylate cyclase type 5 (ADCY5) and C-reactive protein (CRP) as more than 5-fold change (FC) values were observed, also, pathways associated to them were thoroughly studied like MAPK,P13-AKT signaling pathways. Regulatory networks are constructed using these shortlisted genes keeping nodes to be INSR and CRP which tend to give rise to more interacting proteins like IRS1,MED1,ESR1, etc , hence suggesting novelty in predicting onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus therapy.